

SHELL-BASED COMPUTATIONAL HOMOGENISATION WITH IMMERSED METHODS FOR MESO-SCALE MODELLING OF FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

International Conference on Composite Materials, 2023, Belfast

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Contents

- Immersed methods
 - Application to meso-scale models of fibre composites
- Homogenisation of shells/plates
- Results
- Conclusions

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Meso-scale models of advanced fibre composites

Why meso-scale models?

- Estimating stiffness properties
 - Parameter study
- Monitor stresses
- Study damage mechanisms and evolution

Challenges

- Generating bundle geometry
 - Interpenetration
- Discretisation
 - Poor mesh quality/condition number
 - Manual/Semi-automatic meshing
 - Voxel methods

Stig et al. (2012)

Wintiba et al. (2017)

Investigation of Immersed methods!

Immersed methods?

Immersed methods: Finite cell method, Cut-FEM, Immersogeometric, c.f. *Rank et al. (2012)*

+ Benefits

- Fully automatic discretisation of the matrix

- Drawbacks

- Many quadrature points (~50-100M quadrature points for large 3d problems)
- Elements with low volume fraction (ill-conditioned matrix system)
 - (solved with stabilization methods)

Prototype - Immersed methods for 3D woven composite

Bundles

Boundary-fitted mesh with e.g. FE-elements/IGA.

Matrix

Immersed method

Interface

Couple with e.g. penalty or Nitsche's method

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Multi-scale modelling with shells/plates

Figure. Illustration of homogenisation of plates.

Multi-scale modelling with plates

Variational consistent homogenisation

A framework for deriving the two scale formulation from the “fully resolved form”.

- $\int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\delta \mathbf{u}) d\Omega = \int_{\Gamma_N} \delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{t}_p d\Gamma + \int_{\gamma} \delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{t}_p d\Gamma$
- $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}^M + \mathbf{u}^s$
- $\mathbf{u}^{RM} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} + \bar{w} \mathbf{e}_3 - z \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$
- First order homogenisation
- ...

Macro-scale formulation

$$\int_A \bar{\mathbf{N}} : \delta \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \bar{\mathbf{V}} \cdot (\delta \bar{\mathbf{g}} + \delta \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) - \bar{\mathbf{M}} : \delta \bar{\boldsymbol{\kappa}} dA = \text{external forces}$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{N}} = \frac{1}{A_{\square}} \int_{\Omega_{\square}} \boldsymbol{\sigma} d\Omega \quad \bar{\mathbf{V}} = \frac{1}{A_{\square}} \int_{\Omega_{\square}} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 d\Omega$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{M}} = \frac{1}{A_{\square}} \int_{\Omega_{\square}} z \boldsymbol{\sigma} + (\boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{e}_3) \otimes (\mathbf{x} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}) d\Omega$$

Micro-scale formulation

$$\int_{\Omega_{\square}} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\delta \mathbf{u}^s) d\Omega = \int_{\Gamma_{\square}} \mathbf{t}_p \cdot \delta \mathbf{u}^s d\Gamma$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{u}}_{\square}(\mathbf{u}^s) = 0, \quad \bar{w}_{\square}(\mathbf{u}^s) = 0 \quad (\text{Rigid body constraints})$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{\square}(\mathbf{u}^s) = 0, \quad \bar{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}_{\square}(\mathbf{u}^s) = 0, \quad \bar{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}_{\square}(\mathbf{u}^s) = 0 \quad (\text{Boundary conditions})$$

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\square}(\mathbf{u}^s) = 0 \quad (\text{Volume constraint})$$

Multi-scale modelling with plates

Variational consistent homogenisation

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- $\int_{\Omega} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\delta \mathbf{u}) d\Omega = \int_{\Gamma_N} \delta \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{t}_p$
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- First order homogenisation
- ...

Read more in:

[1] Börjesson, E., Larsson, F., Runesson, K., Remmers, J. J. C., Fagerström, M. Variationally consistent homogenisation of plates, **Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering** (2023)

Macro-scale formulation

$$\int_A \bar{\mathbf{N}} : \delta \bar{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \bar{\mathbf{V}} \cdot (\delta \bar{\mathbf{g}} + \delta \bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}) - \bar{\mathbf{M}} : \delta \bar{\boldsymbol{\kappa}} dA = \text{external forces}$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{N}} = \frac{1}{A_{\square}} \int_{\Omega_{\square}} \boldsymbol{\sigma} d\Omega \quad \bar{\mathbf{V}} = \frac{1}{A_{\square}} \int_{\Omega_{\square}} \boldsymbol{\sigma} \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 d\Omega$$

Meso-scale formulation

$$\int_{\Omega_{\square}} \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\delta \mathbf{u}^s) d\Omega = \int_{\Gamma_{\square}} \mathbf{t}_p \cdot \delta \mathbf{u}^s d\Gamma$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{u}}_{\square}(\mathbf{u}^s) = 0, \quad \bar{w}_{\square}(\mathbf{u}^s) = 0 \quad (\text{Rigid body constraints})$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{h}}_{\square}(\mathbf{u}^s) = 0, \quad \bar{\boldsymbol{\kappa}}_{\square}(\mathbf{u}^s) = 0, \quad \bar{\boldsymbol{\gamma}}_{\square}(\mathbf{u}^s) = 0 \quad (\text{Boundary conditions})$$

$$\bar{\boldsymbol{\theta}}_{\square}(\mathbf{u}^s) = 0 \quad (\text{Volume constraint})$$

Results – Plate stiffness properties

Bundle mesh:

- Linear Tetrahedral ~
- Transversely isotropic material:
 - $E_1 = \sim 115$ GPa
 - $E_2 = \sim 8$ GPa
 - $\nu_{12} = \sim 0.29$
 - $\nu_{23} = \sim 0.46$
 - $G_{12} = \sim 2$ GPa

Immersed matrix mesh:

- 30x50x30 elements
- 2nd order IGA-Elements
- Linear elastic material:
 - $E = 3100$ MPa
 - $\nu = 0.35$
- ~ 30 M Quadrature points

Membrane $\bar{\epsilon}$

Bending κ

Shear γ

Effective beam properties in longitudinal direction

	Membrane stiffness EA [N]	Bending stiffness EI [Nmm ²]	Transverse shear KGA [N]
Immersed mesh	127793	434138	
Pure tetrahedral matrix mesh	128382	412725	
Difference [%]	< 1 %	~ 5.1 %	

Conclusion and outlook

Multi-scale homogenisation for plate-elements using VCH.

Automatic discretisation scheme for matrix material for meso-scale models.

- Simple and flexible way of obtaining discretisations for meso-scale models of advanced fibre composites.
 - Show good agreement with standard FE-models
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- Apply the methodology to other complex meso-scale structures.
 - Extend the method to non-linear simulation
 - Interface separation
 - Damage in bundles

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